

Milestone 8.1: MS36 Workplan for strategic and sustainable access is prepared and communicated to all WPs

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ATMO ACCESS
Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

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1 Introduction

The aim of this M8.1 is to ensure the ATMO-ACCESS loop is well understood by all partners as a basis for providing guideline for strategic access plan for access provision to atmospheric RIs and delivering options for sustainable RI access strategies to atmospheric facilities

2 The ATMO-ACCESS loop

During all meetings, the pilot dimension of ATMO-ACCESS was regularly mentioned, insisting on the fact that pilot access modalities must be defined and tested and that feedbacks from providers and users are expected for corrective actions and for establishing guidelines.

The workplan for strategic and sustainable access discussed at the kick-off meeting and during the first SSC meeting is straightforward:

- Implemented a first call for access as soon as possible in the project to ensure momentum and first expectations are met in the consortium. ATMO-ACCESS comes after several years of lacking a TNA/VA program in the community (with the exceptions of Atmospheric Simulation Chambers) and obvious difficulties for staff exchange due to COVID crisis. ATMO-ACCESS is strongly expected by the atmospheric research community and the first call for access was then not targeted
- General calls, open to all scientific questions should be maintained all through the project to respond to scientific needs
- Specific (topical) call targeting specific users or needs must be regularly open. Innovative calls must be encouraged to reach new communities and/or test new ways of implementing TNA, still considering EC financial rules. Innovative approaches must target all type of access: physical, remote and
- Modalities for evaluating success must be implemented from the definition of calls. Similarly, modalities for collecting feedbacks from users must be clear and timely so that corrective actions can be implemented during the course of the project.
- WP2 is centrally collecting and integrating feedbacks and feed WP4,5 and 6 for defining modalities for innovative calls and WP9 and 10 for feedbacks on call organization.
- While objective of ATMO-ACCESS is clearly to use TNA/VA experiences for defining guidelines and options for sustainable access, basic consideration on supporting excellence through competition must remain meaning 1) not all request for TNA will be served and 2) the number of access to specific facilities indicated in the proposal is just indicative and will evolve upon demand. Evaluation of demand will be reviewed in the second phase of the project
- Innovative and very specific calls may have limited demand from users, and this must be integrated in the future options for a sustainable access program
- Defining the best options for sustainable funding must consider the new financial mechanisms proposed in Horizon Europe: CO-FUND, LUMP-SUM, CASCADE-GRANT in particular. WP3 is essential to check with countries best options for enlarging participation in funding access
- ATMO-ACCESS must be in capacity to propose financial guidelines for sustainable access as early as possible in the project.